

USE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Annotation: This article provides complete information about the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in teaching natural sciences in elementary grades.

Key words: Innovation, natural sciences, exhibition, method, pedagogy

In the process of globalization in which we are living, advanced works are being carried out in every field, the time itself demands this, and the young generation is leading in every field. Because our society is rich in the flow of information. The role of the teacher in raising a mature and perfect person in all respects, as our society demands, is incomparable.

As the times are rapidly changing, the field of education is also changing with it and requires the teacher to change his activities. Abdulla Avloni, who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek pedagogy, wrote in his work "*Turkish Gulistan or Morality*" that "cultivating children's ability to think and regularly engaging in this education is a necessary and sacred task. The current era requires every professional to improve their entrepreneurship, knowledge and professional skills.

Today, the main task of a teacher is not only to teach, but also to know how to use new innovative pedagogical technologies, which requires proper organization and management of the educational process. In order to implement these works, extensive works are being carried out in our country, in particular, in cooperation with the Ministry of Public Education and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), effective works are being carried out on the basis of the "Child Friendly School" program.

In this program, great attention is paid to the issues of effective organization of lessons, appropriate use of interactive methods. In particular, the use of interactive methods in teaching students in schools and academic lyceums makes it easier for them to understand this subject.

For the formation of a civil society and a legal democratic state in Uzbekistan, the priority of education is not only ensured, but the pedagogy of the whole society has emerged as a social order.

This means that it is necessary to ensure the process of bringing up the young generation to adulthood with new pedagogical measures. The correct implementation of pedagogical technology in the field of education of our country: - is of great importance in realizing the intellectual potential of our society; - leads to the formation of an independent thinking free person in the society; - leads a person to perfection and accelerates the process of finding his place in life; - ensures the formation of civil society and the construction of a legal democratic state; - having a positive effect on the socio-political climate, the existing social environment in our country will change for the better.

Pedagogical technology is a product of modern didactics and pedagogic development. It can be considered as a new stage on the way to the implementation of practical tasks at a higher level in all the main areas of pedagogy that have existed so far and are being improved. Pedagogical technology, first of all, should be considered a social phenomenon consisting of the activities of people (pedagogues, parents, the public) to meet the needs of further development of education.

The use of innovations in the teaching of natural sciences can mainly affect the younger generation's learning and increase their interest in science. Humanization of pedagogical relations ensures quality education for every student. It creates a free environment for the student and the opportunity to freely express his opinion.

Humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations in the field of education embodies the humanitarian ideas of philosophy, psychology and pedagogy. The focus of these ideas is the goal and task of raising mature people who have the ability to think independently and broadly, who live consciously.

Through the humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations, the creation of cooperation, care in the pedagogical process, the respect and honoring of the students' personality, and the social-psychological and friendly environment conducive to the study, creativity and self-development of the individual. environment is created. In this process, the student is considered the subject of his educational activity, and two subjects of a single educational process with the teacher solve educational tasks in cooperation. In order for the teacher to work on the basis of pedagogical technology, he must first of all be able to form a motive in the student.

Natural sciences is a research science that studies the interaction of living beings with the environment. It is difficult to understand all the learned parts and their functions when learning with a textbook with one-dimensional images. Science textbooks are full of pictures and diagrams. Imagine a virtual representation of the human body in three dimensions, with every activity learned.

Students remember such presentations for a long time. It is somewhat difficult to understand animate and inanimate nature by reading from a textbook. If visual images are used, the ideas will be more vivid and understandable. We believe that the optimal options for the use of innovations in the improvement of natural sciences education conducted in the Russian Federation are applied to the educational process based on their main work experience and the results of scientific research work, which is a positive contribution to the international requirements for the improvement of education

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